

RADIO BROADCAST NARRATIVES AND STAKEHOLDER COMMUNICATION IN WILDLIFE CONSERVATION FINANCE: CHALLENGES AND INNOVATIONS IN NIGER DELTA, NIGERIA

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Abstract: This study examined radio broadcast narratives and stakeholder communication in wildlife conservation finance: challenges and innovations in Niger Delta, Nigeria. The participatory communication theory was anchored in this study. The qualitative research design adopted was grounded in the interpretivist paradigm, utilising in-depth interviews. The population of the study included radio broadcasters, community leaders, environmental NGO representatives and government conservation officers in the Niger Delta region, estimated at 2,000 individuals across Akwa Ibom, Cross River, Bayelsa Delta and Rivers States. A purposive sampling technique was employed to select 30 key informants considered most knowledgeable and actively involved in radio production, environmental advocacy and stakeholder engagement in conservation projects. Data were collected through semi-structured interview guides tailored to each category of respondent, allowing flexibility to probe emergent themes. The interviews were audio-recorded, transcribed verbatim and analysed using thematic content analysis, which involved identifying, coding and categorising recurrent patterns and themes from the narratives. The findings revealed that radio broadcasts in the Niger Delta employed a mix of storytelling, emotional appeals and indigenous language use to effectively communicate wildlife conservation messages. Local folklore and metaphors are often used to relate the importance of conservation to cultural heritage, while emotional narratives around endangered species and forest destruction are designed to evoke urgency and concern. However, while these strategies attract attention, their effectiveness in fostering long-term behaviour change is limited without consistent follow-up and localised, actionable messaging. This study concluded that radio broadcasts in the Niger Delta employed culturally relevant narrative structures, such as storytelling, indigenous language use and emotional appeals to raise awareness about wildlife conservation. These strategies, while effective in attracting attention, face challenges in fostering long-term behaviour change due to the lack of actionable and consistent messaging. The study recommended that radio stations in the Niger Delta should collaborate with conservation organisations to develop consistent, actionable messaging that encourages long-term behaviour change in wildlife conservation, with the support of the National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA).

Keywords: Radio Broadcast, Narratives, Stakeholder Communication, Wildlife Conservation, Finance, Challenges, Innovations

Introduction

Wildlife conservation has emerged as a global imperative, with significant emphasis on the need for sustainable financing and effective stakeholder communication to counter biodiversity loss and ecological degradation. In the era of the Sixth Mass Extinction, the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES, 2019) estimates that approximately one million animal and plant species face extinction. The financing gap for global biodiversity conservation remains substantial, ranging from \$598 billion to \$824 billion annually (Deutz et al., 2020). Amid these challenges, the strategic use of media, particularly radio, plays an instrumental role in shaping public narratives, educating communities and mobilising financial and policy support for wildlife conservation efforts across diverse socio-political contexts.

Globally, radio remains one of the most accessible and cost-effective communication platforms, especially in developing regions with limited digital penetration. According to the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 2022), radio reaches over 75% of the world's population and serves as a vital tool in promoting inclusive dialogue and stakeholder engagement. In conservation discourse, radio narratives often serve to mediate knowledge between conservation scientists, policymakers, local communities and financiers. When framed strategically, these narratives can trigger behavioural change, create awareness and encourage participation in sustainable conservation financing initiatives (Sunderland et al., 2021). The link between storytelling in media and conservation behaviour is thus increasingly recognised as a critical component of environmental communication strategies.

In Africa, where biodiversity is both a source of cultural identity and economic sustenance, radio continues to play a pivotal role in public communication and community mobilisation. The African Union's Agenda 2063 underscores the importance of environmental sustainability, urging member states to enhance public awareness and stakeholder collaboration in biodiversity protection. Despite this, the continent continues to suffer from chronic underfunding of conservation projects, largely due to fragmented communication channels and weak financial infrastructures (OECD, 2021). The dependence on donor-driven financing without long-term domestic strategies has compounded the vulnerabilities of wildlife conservation initiatives across the continent. Effective communication through trusted channels like radio is therefore indispensable in galvanising public support and influencing policy development.

Nigeria, home to diverse ecological zones and endemic species, faces similar conservation and communication challenges. The Niger Delta region, in particular, embodies a paradox of rich biodiversity and severe environmental degradation. Oil exploration, illegal hunting, deforestation and urbanisation have devastated local wildlife populations (Nigerian Conservation Foundation, 2020). While several non-governmental organisations (NGOs) and governmental bodies, such as the National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA), have initiated conservation programmes, the disconnection between these

institutions and local communities continues to undermine their impact. This disconnection is partly due to inadequate stakeholder communication and underutilisation of community-based media like radio.

Radio broadcasting in the Niger Delta is culturally significant and widely accessible, often serving as the primary source of information for rural populace. Local-language programming and narrative-driven formats resonate deeply with community members, allowing for contextualised communication that reflects indigenous values and knowledge systems (Agbo & Olatunji, 2021). Yet, despite its potential, radio is underleveraged in conservation financing discourse, with few programmes focusing on the nexus between environmental conservation, economic empowerment, and community involvement. Where such initiatives exist, they are often fragmented and poorly coordinated, lacking the narrative coherence necessary to sustain stakeholder interest and financial commitment.

Stakeholder communication in the context of conservation finance encompasses the processes by which information is exchanged among actors such as government agencies, NGOs, community members, private sector entities and international donors. The quality of this communication significantly affects transparency, accountability and trust, all of which are crucial for effective conservation financing (Redford et al., 2020). In the Niger Delta, historical grievances, environmental injustices and political instability complicate stakeholder relationships, making effective communication strategies not just important but essential. Radio narratives, if properly crafted, can bridge these divides and facilitate a shared understanding of conservation goals and financial needs.

Conservation finance, broadly refers to the mechanisms and instruments used to generate, manage and allocate financial resources for biodiversity conservation. These mechanisms include payments for ecosystem services (PES), biodiversity offsets, conservation trust funds, green bonds and international aid (UNEP, 2020). However, many of these instruments require strong institutional frameworks and stakeholder buy-in to function effectively. In the Niger Delta, where trust in public institutions is weak and financial literacy levels vary, media narratives have a critical role in demystifying these complex mechanisms and framing them in culturally relevant terms that local communities can understand and support.

Innovations in conservation finance are increasingly tied to communication technologies and participatory storytelling models. Globally, digital storytelling, citizen journalism and trans-media campaigns have shown promise in raising awareness and funding for biodiversity projects (Maffey & Freeman, 2020). However, in regions like the Niger Delta where digital access is limited, traditional media such as radio can serve as a launch-pad for hybrid communication models that integrate indigenous storytelling, participatory governance and financial education. Such approaches offer a pathway to fostering co-ownership of conservation efforts and ensuring that funding models are inclusive and locally adapted.

The intersection between narrative framing and stakeholder communication is crucial in shaping perceptions about the value of biodiversity and the urgency of conservation finance. The way messages are constructed influences how audiences interpret and respond to them (Entman, 1993). In the context of radio broadcasts,

narratives that emphasise communal benefits, ancestral stewardship and intergenerational equity are more likely to resonate with rural audiences in the Niger Delta. These frames can also counteract apathy and scepticism by aligning conservation finance with local aspirations and identities, thus, creating a fertile ground for collective action.

Despite the theoretical recognition of radio's potential, empirical studies on its actual impact in advancing conservation finance in Nigeria remain sparse. Existing literature has focused predominantly on media coverage of environmental degradation or the role of NGOs in biodiversity protection often neglecting the strategic integration of communication and financing frameworks (Akpoveta & Osakwe, 2022). This knowledge gap highlights the need for interdisciplinary research that combines communication studies, environmental economics, and community development to explore how broadcast narratives influence stakeholder engagement and funding outcomes in wildlife conservation.

This study, therefore, seeks to examine how radio broadcast narratives can be strategically employed to enhance stakeholder communication and address the financing challenges of wildlife conservation in the Niger Delta. It is motivated by the urgent need to develop context-sensitive communication models that can mobilise both local and international stakeholders, inform public policy and inspire sustainable financial commitments. By focusing on the interrelationship between narrative structures, communication efficacy and conservation finance, this research contributes to an emerging body of knowledge aimed at environmental sustainability through media innovations.

Ultimately, this study fills a critical research void by investigating not just what is communicated about wildlife conservation in radio narratives but how it is communicated, to whom and with what financial implications. In doing so, it highlights the transformative potential of community-based media in addressing the multifaceted challenges of conservation finance in ecologically fragile and socio-politically complex regions like the Niger Delta. It underscores the importance of narrative framing, participatory communication and media accessibility in fostering a conservation culture rooted in both ecological awareness and financial pragmatism.

Statement of the Problem

Wildlife conservation financing in Nigeria, particularly, in the Niger Delta region, faces a multiplicity of challenges that are deeply rooted in institutional, economic, communicative and environmental complexities. Despite the global emphasis on biodiversity protection and sustainability, the flow of funds and the strategic deployment of resources for wildlife conservation in Nigeria remain insufficient and poorly managed (Roe et al., 2020). The Niger Delta, characterised by its rich but fragile ecosystems suffers disproportionately due to oil exploration, urbanisation, deforestation and climate change. Although radio broadcast narratives have emerged globally as powerful tools for environmental education and stakeholder engagement, their strategic integration into wildlife conservation finance mechanisms in Nigeria remains underexplored. There is a paucity of empirical studies that interrogate how radio broadcasts can influence conservation financing by shaping public

perception, mobilising community participation and facilitating donor engagement, especially, within vulnerable regions like the Niger Delta.

From a methodological standpoint, prior studies on wildlife conservation in Nigeria and Sub-Saharan Africa have predominantly relied on either ecological surveys or institutional financial reports with limited integration of communication-based analyses. This presents a methodological gap, as communication, particularly, through mass media like radio is both a mediating and moderating variable in conservation success. Additionally, a population gap exists in that most studies have failed to consider the perspectives of rural and marginalised communities who are both affected by conservation policies and potential agents of change. The conceptual gap lies in the limited understanding of how narrative framing, message repetition, language use and localisation in radio content affect stakeholder response to wildlife conservation finance. Theoretical tensions also persist in the application of communication theories in environmental finance, most studies either adopt a linear transmission model or rely on behavioural change models without accounting for the participatory and dialogic functions of community radio. Thus, there is a need to reconcile these theoretical conflicts within a practical, empirically testable framework that connects broadcast media narratives to tangible conservation outcomes.

Practically, the knowledge void is evident in policy and programmatic actions. Governmental and non-governmental stakeholders alike lack actionable frameworks for leveraging radio as a tool for conservation finance advocacy in local communities. Furthermore, empirical gaps exist in the evaluation of specific radio programmes tailored toward wildlife conservation in Nigeria, with very few studies documenting audience reception, stakeholder responsiveness or financial outcomes linked to media interventions (Adepoju & Olorunfoba, 2019). This study is thus motivated by the urgent need to bridge these interrelated gaps, methodological, theoretical, empirical and practical through a multi-disciplinary exploration of radio narratives and stakeholder communication. By focusing on the Niger Delta, the study contextualises the urgency of environmental degradation and the imperative for innovative, localised communication strategies to enhance wildlife conservation financing. The research investigates not only how narratives shape stakeholder behaviour but also how they can be optimised to address the financing shortfalls undermining Nigeria's conservation efforts.

Research Questions

1. How do radio broadcast narratives influence stakeholder awareness, perception, and participation in wildlife conservation finance initiatives in the Niger Delta? (Addresses the conceptual and empirical gaps by focusing on narrative framing, audience response and behaviour indicators such as awareness levels, engagement in conservation programmes and contribution to conservation funding.)
2. What role does radio play as a communication tool in mobilising local communities and institutional stakeholders towards sustainable wildlife conservation financing in the Niger Delta? (Targets the practical and population gaps by investigating communication dynamics, stakeholder inclusivity and the effectiveness of radio in reaching marginalised groups.)

3. To what extent do existing radio programmes on wildlife conservation reflect participatory communication models and how can these models be optimised for improved conservation finance outcomes? (Addresses the theoretical and methodological gaps by examining the communication models used, their participatory nature and their correlation with conservation funding and stakeholder actions.)

Wildlife Conservation Finance (Dependent Variable)

Wildlife conservation finance refers to the systems, mechanisms and resources mobilised to support biodiversity preservation and environmental sustainability. Globally, this concept has evolved from traditional government-led funding structures to more innovative and decentralised models involving public-private partnerships, green bonds, conservation trust funds and blended finance approaches (OECD, 2019). Conservation finance is now widely acknowledged as essential in tackling the persistent funding gap in biodiversity preservation, estimated at between \$598 billion to \$824 billion annually (Deutz et al., 2020). Despite these efforts, funding remains disproportionately low in biodiversity hotspots like the Niger Delta, where environmental degradation and wildlife depletion are escalating due to oil exploration and deforestation.

In the African context, conservation finance faces additional constraints, including weak institutional frameworks, poor public engagement and inadequate access to international environmental funds. Many initiatives depend heavily on donor funding without structured long-term financing strategies or community inclusion (Roe et al., 2020). This often leads to fragmented conservation efforts with minimal impact at the grassroots level. The limited understanding of conservation finance among local populations also impedes their willingness and capacity to participate in financing mechanisms. In the Niger Delta, where poverty and environmental injustice intersect, mobilising sustainable wildlife finance requires a shift toward inclusive, communicative strategies that empower local communities and integrate indigenous knowledge systems.

This study conceptualises wildlife conservation finance as the cumulative outcome of financial flows (domestic, international and local), public participation in conservation funding and the effectiveness of fund utilisation for measurable ecological outcomes. The variable is influenced not only by the availability of capital but also by communication dynamics that shape stakeholder awareness, trust and behavioural commitment. Recognising conservation finance as both a financial and communicative process expands the analytical lens beyond monetary resources to include the communicative infrastructures, such as radio that mediate stakeholder understanding and action (Buscher & Fletcher, 2019).

Radio Broadcast Narratives and Stakeholder Communication (Independent Variables)

Radio remains one of the most influential media platforms in Africa, particularly, in rural and semi-urban regions where literacy levels and internet penetration are limited. Broadcast narratives, described as structured storylines embedded within radio programmes, serve as powerful tools for agenda-setting and behaviour change (Couldry, 2008). In the context of wildlife conservation, the way issues are framed, whether through dramatised storytelling, expert interviews or community testimonies affects how audiences perceive ecological threats and conservation financing. Radio narratives that localise content using indigenous languages and culturally

resonant metaphors are more likely to inspire listener engagement and financial contributions to conservation efforts.

Stakeholder communication complements these narratives by fostering two-way information flow between media producers, institutions and the public. Effective stakeholder communication involves building trust, sustaining feedback mechanisms and ensuring the inclusivity of marginalized voices, especially, indigenous and local communities who are most affected by biodiversity loss (Reed et al., 2009). In the Niger Delta, where trust in government institutions is generally low, radio presents an opportunity to bridge the gap through community radio formats and participatory programming. This enhances transparency and enables collective decision-making, which is critical for sustainable wildlife financing.

For this study, the independent variable is conceptualised as the synergy between radios broadcast narratives and stakeholder communication practices. The assumption is that well-structured and culturally relevant radio narratives backed by open, participatory communication channels can improve stakeholder awareness and promote behavioural change that translates into tangible conservation financing. Such communication builds emotional and cognitive resonance, fostering a sense of ownership and responsibility among listeners, which is essential for sustainable environmental stewardship (Manyozo, 2012).

Framework of Relationship between Variables

The conceptual relationship between radio narratives, stakeholder communication and conservation finance is grounded in communication-for-development theory, which emphasises participatory and dialogic models over top-down approaches (Servaes, 2008). Radio programmes that feature local stories, experts and community dialogues can stimulate public interest and institutional support for conservation. This framework proposes that the nature and quality of broadcast narratives, along with interactive stakeholder engagement, positively correlate with community-driven financing behaviour, donor trust and sustainable use of conservation funds.

Earlier communication models, such as the Shannon-Weaver linear model, viewed media as a one-way transmission mechanism. However, contemporary frameworks advocate for participatory communication, especially in environmental contexts where public input is vital for policy and behavioural compliance (Fraser & Restrepo-Estrada, 1998). This study's framework aligns with this shift by treating listeners not as passive recipients but as co-creators of knowledge and action in wildlife conservation finance. In the Niger Delta, this approach is particularly significant due to the historical marginalisation of local voices in environmental governance.

The conceptual framework posits that broadcast narratives (message framing, frequency and localisation) and stakeholder communication (engagement, trust and feedback) interact to influence the dependent variable, wildlife conservation finance (awareness, mobilisation and utilisation). This relationship is mediated by cultural relevance, message trustworthiness and participatory openness. The framework serves as a guide to understanding how communication strategies can be operationalized to close conservation funding gaps through increased stakeholder involvement and behavioural transformation.

Participatory Communication Theory

This theory was originally developed and advanced by theorists such as Paulo Freire (1970) and later expanded by Jan Servaes (1999, 2008). The thrust of the theory lies in the idea that development communication should not be a one-way transmission of information from sender to receiver, but a dialogic and inclusive process where community members are actively involved in designing, interpreting, and acting on information relevant to their lives. Freire emphasised that communication should empower the oppressed through dialogue, critical reflection and co-creation of knowledge, a notion central to environmental and conservation issues where local communities are stakeholders. Servaes (2008) expanded this by highlighting the importance of culturally embedded communication strategies that account for diversity and ownership. In the context of this study, participatory communication is crucial in ensuring that radio broadcast narratives do not merely inform but engage communities in co-creating solutions and financing mechanisms for wildlife conservation in the Niger Delta.

Empirical critiques of the theory point to its implementation challenges, particularly, in hierarchical societies or institutions where participation is often symbolic rather than substantive (White, 2004). Some scholars argue that power imbalances, lack of access to media platforms, and inadequate training in participatory methods often limit the real-world applicability of the theory (Gumucio-Dagron & Tufte, 2006). However, its relevance to this study is strong. Radio, especially, in low-literacy regions can become a participatory platform when used for community storytelling, call-ins and debates that empower stakeholders to engage in conservation finance. By aligning radio narratives with participatory principles, communication becomes a vehicle for both awareness and behavioural transformation, fostering trust and accountability in conservation funding structures. Thus, the Participatory Communication Theory provides a robust theoretical foundation for exploring how dialogic media strategies can stimulate stakeholder-driven solutions to the funding challenges of biodiversity conservation in the Niger Delta.

Empirical Review

Nwankwo (2021) carried out a study on *Community Radio and Environmental Awareness in Rural Nigeria*. This study examined how community radio fosters environmental awareness and participation among rural communities in Nigeria. Method used was descriptive survey design; questionnaires administered to 400 listeners of community radio stations in five rural LGAs in Southeast Nigeria. The study found that local radio programmes in indigenous languages significantly increased environmental awareness and influenced positive ecological behaviour. Critique: While valuable, the study failed to address how such awareness translates into active financial contributions or engagement in conservation funding schemes. Compare and Contrast: Like the current study, it links broadcast media to environmental issues, but it stops short of exploring the financial dimensions of wildlife conservation. Connect: This study supports the conceptualisation of radio as an effective tool for awareness but reveals a gap in understanding its role in mobilising conservation finance, something this research addresses.

Kihika (2018) conducted a research on *Stakeholder Communication and Conservation Success in Kenya's Maasai Mara Ecosystem*. This study investigated the role of stakeholder engagement in the success of wildlife conservation programmes in the Maasai Mara. Method adopted was a qualitative case study using interviews and focus groups with local leaders, conservation NGOs, and park officials. The study revealed that trust-based communication between stakeholders was pivotal in fostering community buy-in and sustaining wildlife conservation programmes. Critique: The focus was predominantly on face-to-face and organisational dialogue with no integration of mass media channels like radio, limiting the generalizability of findings. Compare and Contrast: Both studies centre on stakeholder communication in wildlife conservation. However, your study incorporates mass media narratives, specifically, radio as a communication mechanism, filling a methodological and contextual gap. Connect: This research highlights the importance of stakeholder dialogue, reinforcing the relevance of participatory communication, while your study contributes by extending this dialogue through media systems.

Ujorha and Abdulkadir (2020) did a work on *Financing Biodiversity Conservation in Nigeria: The Role of Media Advocacy*. This study evaluated the role of media advocacy in generating support for biodiversity conservation funding in Northern Nigeria. Method used was mixed methods approach which were content analysis of media campaigns and key informant interviews with conservation stakeholders. Findings revealed that media campaigns led to increased awareness and modest donations but lacked sustainability due to inconsistent messaging and low community participation. Critique: The study offers critical insight into media's fundraising potential but underexplores narrative structure, message framing, and stakeholder-driven content creation. Compare and Contrast: Your study goes beyond mere advocacy to examine narrative construction and participatory storytelling, adding depth to the conversation on conservation finance. Connect: This study signals a trend towards using media for environmental fundraising, and your research addresses the call for more structured, culturally grounded, and participatory radio narratives for sustained stakeholder investment.

Literature Trend and Gaps Identified

Across these studies, there is a trend in leveraging media and stakeholder communication for environmental awareness and conservation. However, a significant gap exists in integrating radio broadcast narratives, stakeholder engagement and financial sustainability into a unified framework, especially, in the Niger Delta context. The empirical literature rarely explores how narrative structures or participatory storytelling can mobilise conservation finance, indicating a theoretical and practical void that your study seeks to fill.

Methodology

The qualitative research design adopted for this study was grounded in the interpretivist paradigm, utilising in-depth interviews to explore the role of radio broadcast narratives in stakeholder communication and wildlife conservation finance in the Niger Delta. This method allows for a rich understanding of the lived experiences, perceptions and communicative interactions between broadcasters, conservation actors and local stakeholders. The population of the study included radio broadcasters, community leaders, environmental NGO

representatives and government conservation officers in the Niger Delta region, estimated at 2,000 individuals across Akwa Ibom, Cross River, Bayelsa, Delta and Rivers States. A purposive sampling technique was employed to select 30 key informants considered most knowledgeable and actively involved in radio production, environmental advocacy and stakeholder engagement in conservation projects. These participants were selected based on their relevance to the study's objectives and their capacity to provide detailed insights. The choice of in-depth interviews aligns with the need to capture nuanced, subjective meanings and to explore the interrelations between media narratives and stakeholder behaviour.

Data were collected through semi-structured interview guides tailored to each category of respondent, allowing flexibility to probe emergent themes. The interviews were audio-recorded, transcribed verbatim and analysed using thematic content analysis, which involved identifying, coding and categorising recurrent patterns and themes from the narratives. This analytic approach supports a detailed understanding of how radio narratives influence stakeholder participation in conservation finance. The justification for choosing qualitative methods, specifically in-depth interviews stems from the exploratory nature of the research, the complexity of the phenomena being studied and the need to contextualise radio narratives within local cultural, social and ecological frameworks. Unlike quantitative methods, which may overlook subtle communicative cues and motivations, this approach enables the researcher to delve into the intricacies of message interpretation, trust-building and collaborative problem-solving in wildlife conservation finance.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Themes were deduced deductively following the research objectives. The following themes were deduced: Narrative Structures and Messaging Strategies in Radio Broadcasts on Wildlife Conservation; Stakeholder Engagement and Participatory Communication through Radio and Challenges and Innovations in Financing Wildlife Conservation via Broadcast Advocacy. These were presented and discussed below:

Narrative Structures and Messaging Strategies in Radio Broadcasts on Wildlife Conservation

This theme explores how radio programmes construct and frame wildlife conservation narratives, including the use of language, storytelling techniques, emotional appeals, indigenous metaphors, and framing strategies. It investigates the stylistic and communicative elements that influence public perception and engagement with conservation issues. Interviews revealed that most radio broadcasters use a combination of storytelling, dramatization and call-in segments to shape their wildlife conservation messages. Storytelling is often anchored in local folklore or indigenous beliefs about forests, animals, and ancestral spirits, which creates a sense of familiarity and emotional resonance with the audience. Broadcasters emphasised that such narrative strategies are essential for making abstract or technical conservation issues understandable and relatable to grassroots listeners who may not have formal education. As one broadcaster in Rivers State noted, "We tell the story of the Niger Delta forest not just as land, but as the heritage of our ancestors. That is how people pay attention."

Several interviewees pointed to the strategic use of indigenous languages, especially Ijaw, Ikwerre, Urhobo and Ibibio, in reinforcing the messages and ensuring inclusive access. Local language broadcasting was cited as a critical tool for encouraging rural participation and trust, especially where English-dominated conservation

campaigns had failed in the past. This approach also facilitates the translation of scientific concepts such as biodiversity loss or ecosystem services into culturally grounded messages. In doing so, the broadcasters help to bridge the knowledge gap between conservation agencies and local communities.

Another dominant strategy identified was the use of emotionally charged narratives. Broadcasters said they intentionally construct stories around endangered species or forest degradation using metaphors of loss, scarcity, and moral responsibility. They often juxtapose images of dying forests with suffering livelihoods to evoke concern and promote a sense of urgency. However, some conservation NGO partners noted that while these emotional appeals grab attention, they do not always lead to sustainable behavioural change or long-term action unless supported by consistent follow-up messaging and community engagement.

The interview also showed that radio messages often follow a problem–cause–solution structure, wherein the broadcasts first outline the threat to wildlife, identify the human or industrial causes, and then propose community or government-based solutions. This structure aligns with persuasive communication theory and appears to work well in prompting discussions among listeners. Yet, some stakeholders argued that the content is sometimes repetitive or too generic, lacking localized data and real-time updates. The study indicates that while narrative structures are powerful, their impact is limited by institutional and editorial constraints within the radio industry.

Stakeholder Engagement and Participatory Communication through Radio

This theme focuses on how various stakeholders such as local communities, government agencies, NGOs, and radio practitioners, interact within the communication process. It examines how inclusive and dialogic the radio broadcasts are and whether they provide spaces for stakeholders to participate, contribute and co-create conservation messages and solutions. Respondents consistently highlighted that radio is one of the few platforms that reaches deep into rural and hard-to-access communities in the Niger Delta, making it ideal for multi-stakeholder engagement in conservation. Interviews with community leaders and conservation NGOs revealed that interactive programmes such as live phone-ins, vox pops and field-based interviews are increasingly used to include the voices of fishermen, hunters, women leaders and youth groups in the dialogue. This participatory communication approach empowers marginalised voices and increases the legitimacy of conservation efforts.

Stakeholders also shared that community-based radio stations tend to be more successful in fostering trust and facilitating engagement than national or commercial broadcasters. This is because local radio is more attuned to the cultural and socio-political dynamics of the region. For instance, one community radio operator in Bayelsa stated, “People trust us because we talk about the issues that affect their daily lives, not abstract policies from Abuja.” Such trust is critical in areas where historical exploitation and environmental injustice have eroded confidence in external conservation actors.

However, the research revealed several challenges. Some NGO partners lamented that despite efforts to engage communities through radio, follow-up participation in conservation activities remains low due to distrust,

economic hardship and lack of institutional support. Many communities see conservation efforts as top-down impositions that do not address their immediate needs. Furthermore, some radio programmes are produced without input from conservation experts or community members, leading to miscommunication or oversimplification of complex issues.

Nevertheless, the study found innovative models where radio stations collaborate with local CSOs to conduct on-ground events that are later broadcast to wider audiences. These initiatives blur the line between media and mobilisation, creating a hybrid communication ecosystem. Such synergies illustrate how radio, when used strategically, can build stakeholder coalitions, share indigenous knowledge and enhance collaborative governance in wildlife conservation. Still, the sustainability of these approaches depends on funding, institutional capacity and continued community involvement.

Challenges and Innovations in Financing Wildlife Conservation via Broadcast Advocacy

This theme addresses the financial dimension, specifically how radio narratives motivate or fail to motivate financial support for wildlife conservation. It explores the barriers (e.g., trust, funding gaps and policy neglect) and emerging strategies or innovations (e.g., crowd-funding, donor engagement and local community pledges) that influence conservation finance through media advocacy. Respondents acknowledged that one of the major limitations in leveraging radio for conservation finance is the general perception of radio as a public service tool, rather than a vehicle for fundraising. Both broadcasters and conservation actors admitted that while radio has succeeded in raising awareness, its use as a platform for financial mobilization is still underdeveloped. Community members, for instance, expect to receive information or support from the radio but do not often view it as a space where they can be asked to donate or invest in conservation initiatives.

Stakeholders explained that socio-economic conditions in the Niger Delta significantly shape public response to appeals for conservation funding. Many residents, already facing poverty and environmental degradation, prioritize daily survival over abstract environmental concerns. As one community elder in Delta State noted, “You want us to donate for animals when we no get food for house?” This economic reality undermines broadcast appeals for financial participation unless they are tied to livelihood benefits or direct community development incentives.

Despite these challenges, some broadcasters and NGOs have begun experimenting with innovative funding approaches, such as partnering with diaspora organizations, launching mobile-based donation campaigns and integrating conservation themes into sponsored community radio dramas. These efforts have had mixed results. While they show promise in attracting donor interest and corporate sponsorship, they often lack continuity due to inconsistent funding, limited technical capacity, and poor metrics for evaluating success.

From the interview, it is evident that radio has untapped potential in shaping narratives that can influence conservation finance, but the sector needs a paradigm shift from passive information delivery to active fundraising and investment engagement. Stakeholders suggested co-creating campaigns with financial institutions, local cooperatives, and environmental influencers to change public perception and behaviour.

Therefore, while the challenges are considerable, the innovations identified in this study signal a growing awareness of radio's evolving role in the sustainability of wildlife conservation finance in the Niger Delta.

Discussion of Findings

The findings reveal that radio broadcasts in the Niger Delta employ a mix of storytelling, emotional appeals, and indigenous language use to effectively communicate wildlife conservation messages. Local folklore and metaphors are often used to relate the importance of conservation to cultural heritage, while emotional narratives around endangered species and forest destruction are designed to evoke urgency and concern. However, while these strategies attract attention, their effectiveness in fostering long-term behaviour change is limited without consistent follow-up and localised, actionable messaging. The findings on the narrative strategies employed by radio broadcasts in the Niger Delta align with Nwankwo's (2021) study, which highlights the critical role of culturally relevant and emotionally compelling storytelling in fostering public engagement in environmental communication. Nwankwo (2021) emphasises that the integration of local narratives and culturally grounded messaging enhances audience connection and participation in conservation activities, which is reflected in the use of local folklore and metaphors in Niger Delta radio broadcasts to evoke an emotional response and raise awareness about wildlife conservation. The relevance of Participatory Communication Theory to the findings on narrative structures and messaging strategies is evident in its emphasis on inclusive, community-driven communication processes. The use of local folklore, indigenous languages, and culturally resonant storytelling in the radio broadcasts aligns with the theory's focus on empowering local communities by making communication relevant to their cultural contexts. Participatory Communication Theory posits that when media content reflects local values and traditions, it fosters deeper engagement and collective action, which is evident in the emotional and cultural appeal of the radio programmes in the Niger Delta. The study found that radio plays a critical role in fostering stakeholder engagement by providing a platform for local communities, NGOs, and government actors to participate in conservation dialogues. Community radio stations, in particular, are more successful in building trust and encouraging participation through interactive programmes like phone-ins and live interviews. However, the challenge remains that many communities view conservation efforts as disconnected from their immediate needs, resulting in limited active participation despite high levels of awareness. The study's finding on stakeholder engagement through radio broadcasts resonates with Kinika's (2018) work on participatory communication and its role in community-based conservation efforts. Kinika (2018) underscores the importance of interactive media platforms, such as radio, in giving communities a voice and enabling two-way communication for effective environmental governance. The study's identification of community radio stations as key facilitators of engagement through interactive programmes mirrors Kinika's argument that participatory media fosters greater community involvement in environmental decision-making. The findings on stakeholder engagement through radio broadcasts are strongly connected to Participatory Communication Theory, which advocates for communication processes that enable

dialogue and interaction among stakeholders. The theory underscores the importance of involving local communities, NGOs, and government actors in the communication process, as demonstrated by the interactive programmes (e.g., phone-ins and live interviews) on community radio stations. These interactive and participatory communication methods, as highlighted in the study, align with the theory's focus on fostering collaboration and inclusive dialogue in environmental governance.

The findings indicate that while radio is successful in raising awareness about wildlife conservation, its potential to mobilise financial support remains underdeveloped. Radio broadcasts are often perceived as public service tools rather than platforms for fundraising, and socio-economic challenges in the Niger Delta limit the public's willingness to engage financially with conservation efforts. However, innovative approaches such as mobile-based donation campaigns and partnerships with diaspora organisations show potential for attracting financial support, though they still face challenges such as funding inconsistency and a lack of continuity. The findings related to the challenges and innovations in mobilising conservation finance via radio align with Ujorha and Abdulkadir's (2020) study, which discusses the potential and challenges of using media for financial mobilisation in environmental conservation efforts. Ujorha and Abdulkadir (2020) acknowledge the power of radio to raise awareness, yet they also highlight the barriers to financial mobilisation, including socio-economic constraints and limited understanding of the link between media advocacy and funding. This is reflected in the study's findings, where radio's role in financial mobilisation is hindered by the public's perception of radio as a public service tool rather than a fundraising platform, and where socio-economic conditions further challenge fundraising efforts. Participatory Communication Theory also informs the findings related to mobilising conservation finance, as it highlights the necessity of creating two-way communication channels that engage communities not only in awareness but also in resource mobilisation. The study's identification of innovative approaches like mobile-based donation campaigns and community partnerships reflects the theory's call for media strategies that go beyond information dissemination to actively involve the public in solving environmental challenges. However, the challenges in shifting public perception about radio's role in fundraising underscore the need for continuous engagement and capacity-building, which Participatory Communication Theory advocates for in mobilising collective action.

Conclusion

The study concludes that radio broadcasts in the Niger Delta employ culturally relevant narrative structures, such as storytelling, indigenous language use, and emotional appeals, to raise awareness about wildlife conservation. These strategies, while effective in attracting attention, face challenges in fostering long-term behaviour change due to the lack of actionable and consistent messaging.

The research explores that radio plays a vital role in engaging stakeholders, particularly through community radio stations, which facilitate dialogues among local communities, NGOs, and government agencies. These interactive programmes create opportunities for participatory communication, although active involvement in

conservation efforts remains limited due to perceived disconnects between conservation initiatives and local needs.

Furthermore, the study identifies that while radio is instrumental in raising awareness about wildlife conservation, its potential to mobilize financial support remains underdeveloped. Socio-economic challenges in the Niger Delta, combined with the perception of radio as a public service tool rather than a fundraising platform, limit its effectiveness in mobilising resources, despite innovative approaches such as mobile donation campaigns showing some promise.

This study makes a significant contribution to the body of knowledge by exploring the unique ways in which radio broadcasts in the Niger Delta utilise culturally relevant narratives and messaging strategies for wildlife conservation. By integrating indigenous languages, local folklore and emotional appeals, the study highlights an innovative approach to communication that is grounded in the cultural context of the region, an aspect often overlooked in broader environmental communication studies. This originality not only enriches the understanding of media's role in conservation but also provides a framework for utilising community-based storytelling to promote sustainable environmental practices, filling a gap in the literature that has often focused on mainstream, top-down communication strategies.

Additionally, the study contributes to Participatory Communication Theory by demonstrating its practical application in stakeholder engagement and the mobilisation of conservation efforts. Through its findings, the research extends the theory's applicability to the context of wildlife conservation in developing regions, particularly by showcasing how local communities, NGOs and government agencies can collaborate through radio broadcasts to foster dialogue and participation. Moreover, the study offers innovative insights into the use of radio as a tool for financial mobilisation in conservation efforts, proposing new approaches to fundraising through mobile-based campaigns and cross-sector partnerships. The development of these instruments and strategies not only advances theoretical understanding but also provides a roadmap for practitioners in environmental communication, ensuring the theory's relevance in real-world conservation contexts.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations have been proffered.

- 1) Radio stations in the Niger Delta should collaborate with conservation organisations to develop consistent, actionable messaging that encourages long-term behaviour change in wildlife conservation, with the support of the National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA).
- 2) Community radio stations should increase their focus on fostering active participation through more interactive programmes and partnerships with local NGOs and government agencies, with the support of the Nigerian Broadcasting Commission (NBC).
- 3) To enhance financial mobilisation for wildlife conservation, radio stations should partner with local businesses, international donors, and government agencies to promote mobile-based donation campaigns, with the guidance of the Federal Ministry of Environment.

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